

SUDTE

Supporting Universities in the
Digital Transformation Erasmus+

The Single Digital Erasmus+ Guidebook

Navigating through the Digital Transformation for Erasmus+ Mobilities

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Digital Transformation in Erasmus+

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**SUDTE –Supporting Universities in the Digital Transformation in Erasmus+
Project Number: 2020-1-TR01-KA203-093849**

“Funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union. However, European Commission and Turkish National Agency cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.”

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ISBN 978-625-00-1002-0

December, 2022

Prepared by Izmir Institute of Technology as part of
Intellectual Output 5 of SUDTE Project

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Editor's Introduction

This guidebook is designed to be a practical source for those who want to get a glimpse of how the digital Erasmus+ tools can be used. We aimed to bring the diverse tools and information under a single guide so as to facilitate the understanding and use of these tools in a more accessible manner.

For this purpose, we will first provide a brief background of how the digital transformation of Erasmus+ started and is continuing. Then, the SUDTE project partner universities will tell their parts of this transformation specifically with regard to the Erasmus Without Paper network.

Looking at the different universities in each university from the perspectives of institutional preparation, the IT departments, International Offices, as well as its economic downsides and upsides will certainly contribute to the knowledge pool that those in need will benefit from.

The later part of the guidebook aims to help both students in their uses of Online Learning Agreement (OLA) and Erasmus+ App, and Erasmus Coordinators and International Office staff in their uses of Dashboard.

We hope that the Single Erasmus Digital Guidebook will accompany the users to better grasp and use the Erasmus' digital tools in an efficient way.

Izmir Institute of Technology
International Office
SUDTE Project Team

Introduction to the Digitalisation of Erasmus+

Introduction to the Digitalisation of Erasmus+

The digitalisation of the Erasmus+ programme was largely triggered by the introduction of substantial changes in the programme in 2014 that led to increased workloads and ever more complex management requirements for International Relations Offices. While initial discussions on the *Erasmus Without Paper (EWP)* topic started already in 2013, the first attempt to digitise a step in the business processes of the programme was initiated with the prototype of the *Online Learning Agreement (OLA)* developed in-house by colleagues at the European University Foundation (EUF). This was taken a step forward with its testing and incremental further development from 2015 onwards thanks to three distinct Erasmus+ Strategic Partnerships and very committed partners¹.

In the meantime, the discussions on EWP had allowed to successfully launch a first project that investigated the technical possibilities for digitally transferring data between Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) instead of handling such processes manually. The main conclusions of this project were drawn in the initial EWP report² and resulted in the creation of the EWP registry³ and the outline of the first Application Programming Interface (API) specifications⁴.

In 2016, the EUF consulted colleagues from the European Commission on the opportunity of developing a mobile application (App) that would support and enhance the mobility experience of students. Since the European Commission intended to launch a Mobile App for the celebration of the 30th anniversary of the Erasmus+ programme in 2017 a new project was born and the first version of the Erasmus+ App was launched in 2017⁵. The App was then maintained by the EUF and a complete overhaul of the tool was initiated in 2020, resulting in the launch of the latest version of the App in January 2021⁶.

In 2019 and 2020, the EUF coordinated the MyAcademicID project funded under the Connecting Europe Facility to work on the identification and authentication mechanism that would put the students at the centre of the business process flows. The project involved key stakeholders of the European Student Card Initiative (ESCI), notably Géant, and resulted in the creation of the MyAcademicID Identification and Authentication platform that allows students to authenticate on services of the OLA or the Erasmus+ App using their home university accounts. It also finalised the generally accepted format and specification of the European Student Identifier.

¹ [OLA 1 project](#); [OLA 2 project](#) and [OLA 3 project](#)

² https://uni-foundation.eu/uploads/2017_EWP%20desk%20research%20final%20version.pdf

³ <https://registry.erasmuswithoutpaper.eu>

⁴ <https://github.com/erasmus-without-paper>

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3Rsu4mm1FG0>

⁶ <https://erasmusapp.eu>

In the meantime, EWP was formally launched during its second project iteration in 2019 and was maintained by the partners involved in its development until the Framework Contract awarded and started by the European Commission in 2022 allowed to reinforce capacity of the partners to support the community and further develop components of the digital infrastructure.

Other tools such as the Erasmus Skills platform⁷ or the living costs database were developed in the meantime to further improve the students' experience when undergoing a mobility period abroad – as well as more technical services like the HEI API were developed to standardise the identification of institutions across networks and platforms and increase their interoperability.

The digitalisation in Erasmus+ was formally adopted by the European Union with the endorsement of the European Education Area⁸ during the 2017 Social Summit in Gothenburg, Sweden. This resulted in the creation of the ESCI⁹ which included key recommendations of the EWP project and paved the way for the establishment of the digitisation roadmap of key processes of the Erasmus+ programme. The definition of the roadmap was a major step forward since it was meant to allow the entire higher education community to prepare for the transition towards digitised workflows starting from 2021. The roadmap is set as follows:

- 2021 - to manage OLAs
- 2022 - to manage inter-institutional agreements (IIAs)
- 2023 - to exchange student nominations and acceptances and transcripts of records related to student mobility

As of 2022, the Framework Contract signed by the EUF on behalf of large consortium of partners with the European Commission allows to cope with the most urgent issues related to the deployment of the network and its services, in particular with regards to the support provided to the higher community (Helpdesk) and the maturity of the connected nodes of the network.

As of 2022, the **key technical components necessary for** the full digitisation of data exchanges in the field of student mobility is summarised as follows:

- Data exchanges via the EWP Network: HEIs operating in-house Information Systems [connect their solution as a node to the network](#); HEIs relying on a commercial provider for their Information System [work with the commercial provider](#) to do so; HEIs (usually smaller ones) not operating any specific system connect via the [Erasmus+ Dashboard](#).

⁷ <https://assessment.erasmuskills.eu>

⁸ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/about/eea-explained>

⁹ <https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/higher-education/european-student-card-initiative>

- To release the European Student Identifier necessary for the accurate identification of users across multiple information systems and simplify authentication of students, HEIs connect their Identity Providers (IPs) via [eduGAIN](#). HEIs not connected to eduGAIN via their [National Research and Education Network](#) may claim a connection via the [IdP of last resort](#).

The future of digitisation will be more akin to a digital transformation process, simplifying drastically the processes underlying student mobility using smart contracts triggering a chain of actions when appropriate stakeholders confirm a student mobility step. These discussions will be led in the context of the stakeholder forum, under the aegis of the European Commission Framework Contract, and involve representatives of Universities, National Agencies, solution providers and other stakeholders. The systems that have been deployed so far will also need to be made fit for purpose for mobilities outside of Erasmus+ as well as at a global scale so that the simplification brought about is concretely enacted and does not require HEIs to work in parallel running systems.

Getting Connected

- **Data Exchange between HEIs and EWP Network Connection**
 - **Case of Selcuk University**
 - **Case of the University of Vigo**
 - **Case of the University of Naples Federico II**
 - **Case of Izmir Institute of Technology**
- **Identification and access management of users**

Getting Connected

Data Exchange between HEIs and EWP Network Connection

Case of Selcuk University

Selcuk University (SU) has been using a third party service provider (i.e. commercial provider) established in Türkiye, for the management of Erasmus Mobilities for more than a decade.

a) Institutional (legal procedures and permissions) level work related to the subject

The use of an external software which is specifically built for Erasmus Programme has been supported by the management of the university although moving to another service providers has sometimes been a topic of discussions due to its cost and functionalities it provides.

To give a brief information about the system; student, and staff mobilities are divided into two separate menus as outgoing and incoming in the commercial software. The information about the student and staff is grouped in different tabs (personal information, student information, contact information, documents, grants, and payments, etc.) and the documents are followed up by the office staff using these menus. The system calculates the student's Erasmus grants, processes Erasmus applications considering the pre-determined definitions such as quota, language threshold, min transcript grade, etc. and allows tracking the mobility processes of the participants.

The use of an automation system supported by technological developments allowed Selcuk University's transition from manual to digitized workflows even before the launch of EWP in 2019. For example, the software has already been connected to the Student Information System (SIS) of our university. That made it easy to gather necessary information of the participants internally and helped with the authentication and identification issues and contributed to the "Paperless Erasmus" motto.

In the process of connecting to the EWP network, some preparations and plans were made at the corporate level and the process was aimed to proceed in a healthy and planned manner. In this context, extensive information was given to the university administration about the EWP network, the importance of this network in Erasmus mobilities and legal procedures. After that, the issue was discussed in a joint working group with the university administration, Erasmus Office and IT unit officials on the details of technical and legal processes. After the legal declaration made by the university administration to the EWP administration for the connection request, the necessary studies for the connection were started.

b) IT Team (Experiences, challenges)

The communication and demand-expectation arrangement between the IT team and the third party provider was carried out under the coordination of the Erasmus Office, and the connection process was started. Signing a contract with the commercial provider including the API implementation steps, durations and costs was one of the most important steps as it set out the framework of the digital transformation. This process is followed by IT integration seamlessly, thanks to several online trainings and functionality tests with partner institutions. Another important step was to get connected to the Edugain which was done by the IT Department of SU. The situation where we are now enables us to process the following digital features:

- Authentication and Identification
- Factsheets
- Inter-Institutional Agreements
- Online Learning Agreement
- Nominations

The further implementations will be carried out once the existing features work without a hustle and the EU commission's announcements to do so.

c) International Relations Office (Experiences, challenges)

After the announcement of the EU Commission about the roadmap for the digital transformation in Erasmus+, SU took the necessary actions immediately and started to implement the EWP standards almost at the earliest time possible. This would not have happened if the following conditions were not met:

- The awareness of the International Relations Office (IRO) staff about the updates in EWP,
- Informing top management and the associated units at the institution about the upcoming deadlines,
- The ability and agility of the 3rd Party Commercial IT company to provide the EWP services.

d) Economical Challenges (the cost of connection, sustainability, etc.)

In a nutshell, getting connected to the EWP network did not require a lot of technical effort for the IRO staff at SU. This was mainly due to the readiness of the Erasmus Office at SU to adapt the digital changes. Of course, everything comes with a price. Compared to the other means of digital transformation, using a 3rd party provider was little costlier, and more importantly it makes the institution to be more dependent on the third-party provider. This means that whenever an update is required for the implementation, the institution must accept the invoice

issued by the company. Otherwise, the institution cannot proceed with the latest technology because the service provider has control of the system. Since the EU Commission will make the digital transformation mandatory, the institution will have no other option but to obey with what the 3rd party service provider requests.

Case of the University of Vigo

a) Institutional (legal procedures and permissions) level work related to the subject

The University of Vigo (UVIGO) decided to use a commercial provider, for the management of Erasmus mobilities, owing to the positive early experiences reported by other Spanish HEIs. Word-of-mouth is commonly sought in Spain as regards the adoption of technological tools in the so-called “digital transformation”, which is supported by national and regional institutions. The Ministry of Education and Vocational Training, for instance, has been offering substantial subsidies since 2020 to public universities for the modernization and digitization of the Higher Education systems. These aids are aimed at promoting investment in infrastructures, technological developments and teaching innovation projects to improve academic resources in digitization; reduce the digital divide for academic staff and students; promote inter-university digital innovation projects of a strategic and interdisciplinary nature; and promote digital training, among other actions.

The Spanish Service for the Internationalization of Education (*SEPIE*, by its Spanish initials) has been acting as the main point of reference for national HEIs in relation to the EWP initiative. In particular, it has been informing their IROs whenever any significant news was published or any useful resources were announced/made available, including the communications of the European Commission or the training materials contributed by the EUF.

The use of the same 3rd party software employed by other Spanish universities (including some of the largest ones) was considered strategic in order to achieve a critical mass that would guarantee proper attention and service. The market of IT services for HEIs is facing strong competition and many providers are coming up with attractive offers for different service packages, even if their software has not achieved a full-proof level of maturity and the documentation falls short to meet the users’ expectations and needs.

That said, UVIGO is making steady progress in its digitization plans, with heavy involvement of its IT department in order to integrate (and help adapt) the tools used for different purposes: staff management, student records, mobility, videoconferencing systems, virtual laboratories and remote software, etc. It is acknowledged that the effort invested in this may influence decisions to switch to alternative solutions in the future.

b) IT Team (Experiences, challenges)

The IT team of UVIGO has been working hand-in-hand with the providers of information services under the supervision of its Chief Digital Officer, in order to achieve full and seamless integration with the in-house systems. A number of data migration and consolidation subsystems have been implemented, which came with significant effort and investment of resources (again, funded by the subsidies mentioned above to support the digital transformation of Spanish HEIs). The main challenges were related to the difficulties inherent to the development of complex software projects, worsened at some points by changes to the specifications of the interfaces intended to guarantee interoperability. The EWP specifications were no exception.

As of November 2022, UVIGO is confident about the status of its tools and processes to handle Erasmus+ mobilities digitally. A follow-up of the interoperability issues detected since the spring of 2022 showed that more than 90% of the incidents were due to pitfalls of the systems on the remote side of the connection.

c) International Relations Office (Experiences, challenges)

The IRO staff of UVIGO has been key in order to achieve the current level of maturity. They have been deeply involved as end users of the tools intended to manage Erasmus+ mobilities, given the horizon that such tools will speed up their work significantly in the future (hopefully, already during the management of the mobilities for the 2022-23 academic year). Nonetheless, the process has been painstaking for them, due to three reasons:

- Firstly, their current workload is high all year round and the number of staff members is limited.
- Secondly, they often have to try new user interfaces for which there is not yet sufficient, complete and detailed documentation.
- Thirdly, they are puzzled by the technical jargon used during the troubleshooting stages, as they find themselves mediating between the IT staff of UVIGO and the development teams of the 3rd-party service provider.

Finally, it is important to highlight the fact that part of the IRO staff has non-permanent contracts, so they may leave their current positions in the future, despite the ample know-how that they have accumulated. The quality of the documentation and the streamlining of the processes are key to ensure smooth transitions, which falls under the responsibility of the IRO directors.

d) Economical Challenges (the cost of connection, sustainability etc.)

So far, the digitization processes have been supported by national and regional funds, but even so the University has to invest significant amounts of resources of its own. There is substantial

evidence that this serves to attain improvements and savings, but there may be risks ahead related to the increased reliance on technological means that are beyond the University's control. Apparently, there is always "one more step" in digitization or specification updates looming ahead, and HEIs play the role of plain consumers. Any future updates will have to be implemented in order not to be left out, and they will come along with invoices from the 3rd party providers. In many cases, there will be no real possibilities to switch to alternative companies because of all the time, effort and resources previously invested to make the former's solutions work together with the in-house systems.

Case of the University of Naples Federico II

a) Institutional (legal procedures and permissions) level work related to the subject

Since 2014, when Erasmus+ program started (2014-2020), University of Naples Federico II (UNINA) has used an Excel-based management tool for the realization of Erasmus mobilities. Starting from 2022, UNINA looked at valuable alternatives to make more efficient Erasmus mobility management, finding in an external provider, the resolution of several Erasmus mobility issues. However, the connection of UNINA's systems to EWP has a pivotal role in the experience of data exchange systems among SUDTE partners and HEIs overall. Following the EU policy about the digitalization strategies, the Italian context also revealed a particular attention to the new digital era for data sharing purposes. Indeed, HEIs in Italy usually prepare a comprehensive Strategic Plan in which digital transformation is included. Nevertheless, not all institutions have had the exact knowledge about this topic and benefits of technology usage in the institutions have not been realized yet. All the activities concerning EWP are carried out through a process that transfers the data of institutions and individuals who want to benefit from mobility to the other institutions. For this reason, various legal regulations have been made for data sharing among partners and need to be made across European HEIs, in general. Due to issues such as validity of digital signatures, data sharing and recognition, various problems have been experienced slowing down the data exchange between HEIs.

b) IT Team (Experiences, challenges)

Regulations regarding processes such as digital signatures, OLAs, IIAs and automatic recognition, permissions-approvals and determinations required for connecting to the EWP network have been carrying out by UNINA's IT team able to serve the institution having more than 10 thousand students and with high level of expertise and technical infrastructure. . As stated above, University of Naples Federico II (UNINA) based all the management of Erasmus flows on Excel-based management tool for the flows derived by student mobilities. Such tool implies a manual updating on excel files, which might be prone to several impeding errors. For this reason, being such tool highly underperforming. Starting from 2022, UNINA used a 3rd party provider, to manage most of the activities related to Erasmus mobility. Since the implementation of this support is very recent, we can consider this assistance as still "experimental". As we write, a part of international student mobility modules may not be object

of the external provider and hence still exist excel files. Thus, we can consider such management tool for Erasmus mobility as a hybrid that allows a next step to the full digital commitments about Erasmus mobilities. With the 3rd party provider, UNINA believes that it will be able to satisfy the needs that the previous system required. For instance, create a network that will enable all the data repositories in whatever form to communicate with each other, either exchange structured data and not primarily documents (e.g., scans) or manage the authentication of servers and users. However, regarding the first early results achieved by the UNINA's third-party provider has implemented all the requested APIs tested and released in 2022. Such reached goal represents the main aspect to underline the improvement in data exchanging activity about the digitalization of Erasmus+ activities. They achieved such results according to the methods required by the EWP project specifications, having developed server-side APIs that are queried by the other partners to retrieve the requested information. Also, they integrated the support for the partners' APIs in order to import all the requested data in their mobility digital module.

c) International Relations Office (Experiences, challenges)

The effectiveness of data sharing among HEIs is also capable to influence the activities of IRO staff, boosting the communication among this office and several stakeholders involved in EWP objectives (department staffs, Coordinators, IT Teams, Teachers). This activity should be monitored in a coordinated manner so that the digitalization processes and digital platforms developed for the Erasmus+ programme can be used in a healthy way. In fact, the Intellectual Output 3 of the SUDTE Project revealed that on one hand the level of awareness of digitalization process and digital skills for data management related to EWP is still inadequate, on the other hand that IRO members wish to get a better data exchanging expertise.

d) Economical Challenges (the cost of connection, sustainability etc.)

Being aware of the importance of data sharing for Erasmus+ purposes, Italy and the EU in general can admit that their objectives on this novel issue are both broad and somewhat tricky. Despite the cost of connection are generally high due to both a technical infrastructure not fully developed and a degree of stakeholders' expertise still in improvement, the focus of whole digitalization process has been directed on an interconnected and sustainable digital society, on a fair and competitive digital economy in which digital data substitutes paper, and an Europe as a global digital player that works for people.

Case of Izmir Institute of Technology

Izmir Institute of Technology (IZTECH) has been using the Dashboard system to join the EWP network since the beginning of this project but by the end of this project, IZTECH has connected its in-house system to the EWP network.

a) Institutional (legal procedures and permissions) level work related to the subject

IZTECH has been using an in-house system to accept student applications to Erasmus+ mobility programs since 2016. IZTECH is one of the few HEIs in Türkiye that employs an online application system produced by the IT department of the institution to accept and manage Erasmus+ applications. IZTECH has joined the SUDTE project with the aim of connecting its in-house student application system to the EWP network. This aim had full support and commitment from the upper management as the only technical institute in Türkiye, because being a frontier in digitalization and information technologies is among its institutional goals. Therefore, IZTECH's IT department joined the project and started writing the necessary infrastructure to connect to the EWP network.

IZTECH started receiving Outgoing Erasmus Student Study Mobility applications through an online in-house system designed by its IT staff in 2016 to save time and paper. Applications for Outgoing Student Placement Mobility and Outgoing Staff Mobility (of both administrative and academic staff) were received through another software purchased in 2016. Due to the high number of Outgoing Erasmus Student Study and Placement Mobility applications, and to the overlapping situations of the two mobility, the idea of creating a Joint Online In-house Study and Placement Mobility Application System emerged in 2019, and the works towards creating one started in 2020. IZTECH's IT team and International Office staff held a series of meetings and workshops together to design a relevant system that could meet the needs of the International Office (IO). CGPA's (Cumulative Grade Point Average) of the applicant IZTECH students, were automatically retrieved from the system thanks to the integration of the in-house system with the IZTECH Student Information System. The in-house system checks the eligibility of the student applications and eliminates the ones that do not meet the application prerequisites. In this way, ineligible applications are not included in further steps such as placement.

As stated above, at the beginning of this project IZTECH was connected to the EWP network through the Dashboard, and this connection was established by the IT department. In order to plan for the development of the necessary software to establish the connection between the in-house system and the EWP network, several meetings have been held between the IT department and the IO. It is important to note that, in terms of administration IO works under the guidance of the Advisor to the Rector on Internationalization while IT department works under the Vice Rector. Therefore, internal communication meetings had to be conducted with all parties involved. Due to unforeseen circumstances, three software developers involved in developing the required software quit the IT department during the SUDTE project. Therefore, a request for a solution was directed to the Computer Engineering department which led to two professors joining the project. However, due to data privacy and legal issues, only the IT department had the necessary permissions to test the system. Therefore, their involvement in the project continued to some extent.

b) IT Team (Experiences, challenges)

The following problems were encountered by the IZTECH IT team in their IZTECH-EWP integration work:

- For the EWP integration, there is information confusion at the stage of connecting to the network, as there is information about the application on different web pages, but it is difficult to find access to the main application page.
- The codes shared by the EUF on Github are written only in Java; there are universities in Türkiye and in the world that use C#(.Net Core), but no sample codes were found in C#(.Net Core).
- No contact point has been found that provides technical support directly to universities in Europe for the integration of EUF's relevant services.
- Once the initial software is developed the next step is testing. Testing gives an indication of whether the software works as intended. However, it is impossible to test a feature because of the system design of EWP. It requires another partner to be able to test, where almost none agreed to do it since it is seen as a waste of time on their side.

c) International Relations Office (Experiences, challenges)

After the announcement of the EU Commission about the roadmap for the digital transformation in Erasmus+, IZTECH initially chose the simple Dashboard connection to start the digitalization project. As stated above, IZTECH has been using an in-house student application system to collect Erasmus+ application. Within the scope of the SUDTE project establishing a connection between the in-house system and EWP was envisioned. This way the EWP connection can be designed in a more user-friendly way. To this end, IZTECH's IT Team and IO staff gathered together to establish the in-house system. Since the in-house system was designed together with the IT Team and the IO staff, no additional training was required for the IO staff. Another advantage of the in-house system connection is that problems encountered can be forwarded to the IT department and minor problems can be solved rapidly. However, due to the technical challenges involved in the EWP connection, IZTECH has not yet completely connected to the EWP network. Therefore, IZTECH needs to use the Dashboard connection to complete some actions.

d) Economical Challenges (the cost of connection, sustainability etc.)

Connecting IZTECH's in-house system to the EWP network proved to be significantly more challenging than initially foreseen. In addition to the technical challenges stated above, three of the four software developers in the IT department quit job unexpectedly, and although IZTECH received support from its Computer Engineering department, continuing to develop a project on unfinished code has had its own significant challenges. While the initial investment

cost for connection of the in-house system has been significantly lower in comparison to the 3rd party service providers, the maintenance can be a problem for smaller institutions with small and busy IT departments. There will be constant improvements in the EWP network as such an ambitious project will definitely require regularly updating the in-house system due to the needs of the significant number of institutions involved. Therefore, updating the system so as to keep up with the EWP network will be a challenge for a small IT department. In addition, testing is a significant problem as stated above, finding constantly testing partners to check on the EWP connection is going to be very difficult. Overall, while using an in-house system has many advantages and can be very user-friendly, in the long run, the maintenance of such a system puts too much pressure on a small IT department. It might be more feasible for a larger university with a bigger IT department.

Identification and access management of users

The success of the digital transformation process that the Erasmus+ programme is undergoing largely depends on the involved institutions' ability to identify the students when moving across multiple institutions. The unique identification of students will make sure data sets which are transferred between institutions are made available to the appropriate students and departments via the developed online services.

In the context of the MyAcademicID project¹⁰, led by the EUF, the format of the ESI¹¹ was standardised with the support of National Research and Education Networks and European stakeholders like Géant. The adoption of a common standard for a ESI was of paramount importance to ensure interoperability between information systems involved in managing student mobility and student services at large.

The decision to implement the ESI will remain with the institutions which decide on whether to release or not this specific attribute when student authenticate on an e-service (like the erasmusapp.eu) using their home student account via eduGAIN. This architecture ensures that there is no central platform for storing all the ESIs and therefore maintains the autonomy of the HEIs in this regard.

The institutions are invited to start releasing the ESI either through the National Research and Education Network in their country¹² or, if such a membership is not possible, via the Identity Provider of last resort¹³ built to serve institutions which cannot be part of eduGAIN.

¹⁰ <https://myacademic-id.eu>

¹¹ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/SM/European+Student+Identifier>

¹² <https://about.geant.org/membership/members-associates-general-assembly-representatives/#National>

¹³ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/SM/IdP+of+Last+Resort>

The technical documentation regarding the European Student Identifier¹⁴ and the identification and access management platform¹⁵ to release the European Student Identifier can be found on the Géant Wiki.

¹⁴ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/SM/European+Student+Identifier>

¹⁵ <https://wiki.geant.org/display/SM/MyAcademicID+Identity+and+Access+Management+Service>

Guiding Students

- **The Online Learning Agreement (OLA)**
 - Logging into your OLA Platform
 - Creating an OLA
 - Making Changes to the OLA
- **Erasmus+APP**
 - How to access
 - How Can I get a European Student Card
 - Other Features

Guiding Students

The Online Learning Agreement (OLA)

The Online Learning Agreement (OLA) is the digital solution built in EWP for the most important steps of Erasmus mobilities: correctly managing the Learning Agreement (which sets out the programme of the studies or the traineeship to be followed abroad) so as to ensure recognition of the ECTS earned without any further recognition requirements. The Learning Agreement must be approved by the student/trainee, the sending institution/organisation/enterprise and the receiving counterpart before the start of the exchange. Changes can be requested exceptionally for various reasons after the exchange has started, but only once.

The OLA is the most convenient way for students/trainees and management offices to create, edit and approve Learning Agreements online, have them signed and proceed with updates. There is no need for any part to print the resulting documents, which look online exactly as they would on paper. The OLAs are always available on the EWP platform to check and download.

Logging into your OLA Platform

At <https://learning-agreement.eu/> there are three options available to access the OLA platform, as shown in the snapshot below:

- Logging in via eIDAS (the EU's "electronic IDentification, Authentication and trust Services" platform) implies using the digital national ID infrastructure of the student's/trainee's country.¹⁶

¹⁶ As of August 2022, this is supported for Belgium, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Germany, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Portugal, Slovakia and Spain.

- Logging in via eduGAIN (the “EDUCation Global Authentication Infrastructure”) entails using the academic credentials managed by the student’s/trainee’s HEI.¹⁷
- Logging in via Google requires using the authentication services provided by Google in the first place, and some additional checks afterwards.

All three options lead to the MyAcademicID platform, which first asks for a double-check of the name and email address. Then, the applicant can agree to the terms of the MyAcademicID Acceptable Use Policy¹⁸. Finally, the applicant must provide some personal information as shown below to create the MyAcademicID account, and agree to the Terms and Conditions¹⁹ as well as to the Privacy Policy²⁰.

Creating an OLA

Once logged in, the student/trainee can notice that, back on <https://learning-agreement.eu/>, the header of the web page now offers links to browse his/her existing learning agreements (if any) to revise the account information, and to log out.

¹⁷ As of August 2022, this is supported for Albania, Austria, Belgium, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Türkiye and the United Kingdom.

¹⁸ Available at <https://wiki.geant.org/display/SM/Acceptable+Use+Policy>

¹⁹ Available at <https://learning-agreement.eu/terms-conditions>

²⁰ Available at <https://learning-agreement.eu/privacy-policy>

Then, the “My learning agreements” option takes to a page with a button that allows to create a new Learning Agreement.

Upon clicking the “Create New” button, the applicant is first asked about the type of mobility. As of August 2022, the following three options are available, in the expectation that new types will be added in forthcoming updates:

- Semester Mobility,
- Blended Mobility with Short-term Physical Mobility,
- Short-term Doctoral Mobility

Each button takes to subsequent pages tailored to the specific Learning Agreement that is needed, going through several stages as shown below for the case of Semester Mobility (note that there is no “Virtual Components” section in Blended Mobilities and Short-term Doctoral Mobilities options):

- Under “Student Information”, the applicant can check the personal data and indicate the academic year in which the mobility is intended (which may not be the current academic year).

Academic year *

2022/2023

Student

First name(s) * Last name(s) *

Email *

Date of birth * Gender * Nationality *

dd/mm/yyyy Undefined Country to which the person belongs administratively and that issues the ID card and/or passport.

Field of Education * Field of Education Comment Study cycle *

Short cycle (EQF level 5)

Field of education: The ISCED-F 2013 search tool available at http://ec.europa.eu/education/international-standard-classification-of-education-isced_en should be used to find the ISCED 2013 detailed field of education and training that is closest to the subject of the degree to be awarded to the student by the Sending Institution.

Study cycle: Short cycle (EQF level 5) / Bachelor or equivalent first cycle (EQF level 6) / Master or equivalent second cycle (EQF level 7) / Doctorate or equivalent third cycle (EQF level 8).

- Under “Sending Institution Information”, the applicant can specify his/her institution’s country, name and faculty/department. Then, he/she must designate a **Responsible Person at the Sending Institution**: an academic who has the authority to approve the Learning Agreement, to exceptionally edit it when it is needed, and to guarantee full recognition of the programme at hand on behalf of the academic unit in charge. This information is normally given by the institution to the applicant as part of his/her nomination process.

- The applicant can optionally designate an **Administrative Contact Person**, i.e. a person who provides a link for administrative information and who, depending on the structure of the HEI, may be the departmental coordinator, or works at the IRO or equivalent unit.

- The tool has an auto-complete feature for the country and Sending Institution, but the responsible persons must be filled in manually with the data provided by the institution.

- The process is repeated under “Receiving Institution Information” for the institution with which the applicant intends to engage as part of his/her Erasmus+ experience.
 - After providing the institutional information, the applicant can build his/her mobility program by indicating the Learning Components (e.g. courses at universities) that s/he intends to take as part of the Erasmus+ experience, and which ones will be

recognized in exchange. The details about learning components should be provided by both the Sending and the Receiving Institution (e.g. in the form of course catalogues).

- Aside from the learning components, the form first requires the start and end dates of the mobility, as well as the language of instruction at the receiving institution and the student's/trainee's level of language competence (A1/A2/B1/B2/C1/C2/Native speaker).
- The student/trainee may add web links to the course catalogues at the Receiving and Sending Institutions, where the learning outcomes are described. S/he may also provide a link to a web page describing the provisions to apply in case s/he does not complete successfully some educational components.

The screenshot displays a multi-step digital form. At the top, a progress bar shows six steps: 1. Student Information, 2. Sending Institution Information, 3. Receiving Institution Information, 4. Proposed Mobility Programme (highlighted in red), 5. Virtual Components, and 6. Commitment. Below the progress bar, the 'Academic year' is set to '2022/2023'. A dark blue header for the current step reads 'Preliminary LA'. Two date pickers are present: 'Planned start of the mobility' and 'Planned end of the mobility', both showing 'dd/mm/yyyy' placeholders. Below these are two sections: 'Table A - Study programme at the Receiving institution' and 'Table B - Recognition at the Sending institution'. Each table section indicates 'No Component added yet.' and features a red 'Add Component to Table A/B' button. There are also text input fields for 'Web link to the course catalogue at the Receiving Institution' and 'Web link to the course catalogue at the Sending Institution', both with a note: 'This must be an external URL, such as http://example.com'. Additionally, there are dropdown menus for 'The main language of instruction at the Receiving institution' and 'The level of language competence', with a link to the CEFR levels page provided.

- The learning components at the Receiving and Sending Institutions must be entered manually, one by one, by clicking on the buttons "Add Component to Table A" (for the receiving side) and "Add Component to Table B" (for the sending side). The requested information, as shown on the right, includes the component's title, its code, the number of ECTS to be awarded or recognized, and the semester.

Table A - Study programme at the Receiving institution *

Component to Table A Remove

Component title at the Receiving institution (as indicated in the course catalogue) *

An "educational component" is a self-contained and formal structured learning experience that features learning outcomes, credits and forms of assessment. Examples of educational components are: a course, module, seminar, laboratory work, practical work, preparation/research for a thesis, mobility window or free electives.

Number of ECTS credits (or equivalent) to be awarded by the Receiving Institution upon successful completion *

Component Code *

Semester *

ECTS credits (or equivalent): in countries where the "ECTS" system is not in place, in particular for institutions located in Partner Countries not participating in the Bologna process, "ECTS" needs to be replaced in the relevant tables by the name of the equivalent system that is used, and a web link to an explanation to the system should be added.

Add Component to Table A

1 — 2 — 3 — 4 — 5 — 6
Student Information **Sending Institution Information** **Receiving Institution Information** **Proposed Mobility Programme** **Virtual Components** **Commitment**

Academic year *

Table C

Component to Table C Remove

Component title or description at the Sending Institution *

Component Code *

Number of ECTS credits (or equivalent) to be recognised by the Sending Institution *

ECTS credits (or equivalent): in countries where the "ECTS" system is not in place, in particular for institutions located in Partner Countries not participating in the Bologna process, "ECTS" needs to be replaced in the relevant tables by the name of the equivalent system that is used, and a web link to an explanation to the system should be added.

Short description of the virtual component *

Automatically recognised towards student degree

Automatic recognition comment

Please add the Table if you wish to indicate virtual component(s) at the receiving institution before, during or after the physical mobility to further enhance the learning outcomes.

Add Component to Table C

- "Virtual Components" (only for Semester Mobility) must be indicated in case the applicant intends to take additional online learning components before, during or after the physical mobility to build up a richer experience. The forms allow indicating the ways of recognition at the Sending Institution as above, making up a Table C.

- The final step is to sign the LA, agreeing to a text that highlights the requirements of the applicant, the Sending Institution and the Receiving Institution, as well as the applicant's rights as a student going on the Erasmus+ program. By clicking on the "Sign and send" button, the applicant sends the OLA to the Responsible Person at the Sending Institution for review.

All three parties signing the Learning Agreement commit to comply with all the agreed arrangements, thereby ensuring that you will receive recognition for the studies successfully carried out abroad without any further requirements.

1 Student Information 2 Sending Institution Information 3 Receiving Institution Information 4 Proposed Mobility Programme 5 Virtual Components 6 Commitment

Academic year *
2022/2023

Commitment Preliminary

By digitally signing this document, the student, the Sending Institution and the Receiving institution confirm that they approve the Learning Agreement and that they will comply with all the arrangements agreed by all parties. Sending and Receiving Institutions undertake to apply all the principles of the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education relating to mobility for studies (or the principles agreed in the Inter-Institutional Agreement for institutions located in Partner Countries). The Beneficiary Institution and the student should also commit to what is set out in the Erasmus+ grant agreement. The Receiving institution confirms that the educational components listed are in line with its course catalogue and should be available to the student. The Sending Institution commits to recognise all the credits or equivalent units gained at the Receiving Institution for the successfully completed educational components and to count them towards the student's degree. The student and the Receiving Institution will communicate to the Sending Institution any problems or changes regarding the study programme, responsible persons and/or study period.

Clear

By clicking on "Sign and send" you also give express consent for your personal data contained herein to be transmitted to the HEI or Organisation of destination.

Previous Sign and send the Online Learning Agreement to the Responsible person at the Sending Institution for review

Back in <https://learning-agreement.eu/>, the applicant can browse the list of OLAs he/she has created, with a Status field indicating whether they have been signed, modified or rejected, and a timeline that allows viewing and comparing successive versions. The final status for an approved OLA is "Signed by both coordinators".

Making Changes to the OLA

An applicant cannot edit an OLA after submitting it. However, coming further in his/her mobility experience, he/she can request exceptional changes for various reasons, but **only once**.

When the OLA has got to the "Signed by both coordinators" status, the applicant can see an "Apply Changes" option on the page under <https://learning-agreement.eu/> that lists his/her OLAs. Clicking on it, subsequent forms allow the following actions:

- Changing the starting and ending dates of the mobility.
- Changing the information of the Responsible Person and the Administrative Contact Person at the Sending Institution and the Receiving Institution.
- Revising the learning components at the Receiving Institution, the recognized components at the Sending Institution, and the table of virtual components. The initial tables remain unchanged for future reference.
- The applicant can select which components from the original tables should be deleted, specifying the reasons for the change ("Previously selected educational component is not available at the Receiving Institution", "Component is in a different language than previously specified in the course catalogue", "Timetable conflict" or "Other").
- The applicant can add new components, choosing as reason "Substituting a deleted component", "Extending the mobility period" or "Other".

The applicant can finally sign the request for changes, agreeing to a text that highlights requirements and rights. By clicking on the sending button, the applicant sends the changes to the Responsible Person at the sending institution for review.

Erasmus+APP

The Erasmus+ App will guide you through your mobility journey and allow you to find all the relevant information and services to make your exchange more enriching and smoother. The Erasmus+ App is owned and funded by the European Commission, and it has been developed under the 30 Years of Erasmus Campaign and is being further enhanced as part of the European Student Card Initiative. **The aim of the application** is to become the single point of entry for participants to access information on Erasmus+ opportunities, as well as to guide them through the processes surrounding their mobility and give them access to information and services.

How to access

1. You can access the Erasmus+ App (<https://erasmusapp.eu/profile>) via **EU Login** by setting an account with your credential.

2. After registering, click on your profile icon and enter more information about your Erasmus.

3. Alternatively, you can also access via your academic credentials (**eduGAIN**) which is the login provided to you by your HEI and will allow you to connect to multiple Erasmus+ online services.

4. From the Erasmus+ App, you will be [connected](#) to where you can access with your eduGAIN account.

5. Once you have logged in with your eduGAIN credentials, you will come to this screen asking you to re-enter your credentials to authorise access.

If you do not have the eduGAIN account, ask your coordinator if your university is already part of the eduGAIN community (most probably it is) and how you can get your credentials.

How to Connect and Communicate with other Erasmus Students

Erasmus+ Journey section

In this section you will find a line with each step of your Erasmus experience:

- Before application,
- During application,
- Before you go,
- During mobility,
- After mobility

a. Before application

You may find the local **Erasmus Student Network (ESN)** section or a similar association at your institution.

These associations are run by volunteers who have often been on a mobility period and are happy to give you tips and advice as well as help you throughout your Erasmus+ mobility. Look out for them before you leave as they can have very valuable insights to share regarding your preferred destinations!

<https://www.youtube.com/c/ESNInternational>

- Go to the tab on the upper left on App+ or click on <https://erasmusapp.eu/journey>,
- Click on Erasmus+ Journey and then click on “Reach out your local Erasmus+ association”

- Click on **Erasmus Student Network (ESN)**

- You will be on the ESN official website (<https://esn.org/sections>). Through the map you will be able to find your ESN section

b. During application

In this section you will find all information you need for the preparation of the application documents. For example, if you click on “get your OLA signed”, you will get all information about what the use of this important document is.

Erasmus+ Journey	
During Application	
Discover possible study destinations	>
Contact your Erasmus + Coordinator	>
Select your preferred host institutions	>
Finalise your application to go study abroad	>
Get nominated	>
Apply to the host institution	>
Get accepted	>
Get your Online Learning Agreement signed	>
Get your Grant Agreement signed	>

Get your Online Learning Agreement signed.

This step is crucial for the recognition of your successfully completed courses abroad. The Online Learning Agreement defines the programme of studies you will follow abroad and what courses they will replace in your study programme at home upon your return. It must be approved by you, your home institution and your host institution before the start of your mobility.

The Online Learning Agreement consists of all of the educational components that will be included

c. Before you go

This section reminds you of everything you need to do before you leave, based on the country you are going to and the city you will live in. For example, if you click on “assess your language level”, you will find link about the Online Linguistic Support (OLS) website to keep up to date on how you can test your language level.

d. During mobility

This section involves information that you need to know during your experience. One of the most important things that you don't forget is the update of your OLA.

e. After mobility – in this section there is all you need to know when your experience will finish and you will be ready to come back home!

For example, if you click on “get your mobility recognized”, you will find information on how to get your university to recognize the examinations you have taken abroad, converting the marks you have obtained and the credits you have earned.

Erasmus+ Journey

Book your return trip >

After mobility

Contact your home institution >

Get your mobility recognised >

Document how the mobility has impacted you and your skills! >

Complete the Erasmus + Participant report >

Join a home Erasmus+ Association >

Share your Erasmus+ enthusiasm! >

Start another Erasmus+ experience! >

How Can I get a European Student Card

From your account, you can click on the card icon. If you initially logged in via your eduGAIN account, you will have the possibility to choose your image to upload.

Your European Student Card

We need to access your camera to take a photo for your European Student Card. Please follow the instructions below:

1. Position your face in the centre of the screen.
2. Remove anything obscuring your face (e.g., sunglasses, hats, scarves etc.)
3. Make sure the lighting is good and your face is clearly visible.

Update your picture

Scegli file Nessun file selezionato

Finally, you will get your European Student Card!

If you did not log in with your eduGAIN account, you will find above how to log in and then go back to the card icon and get your card.

Other Features

The Erasmus+ App provides support to Erasmus+ mobile students participating in Higher Education studies, Higher Education traineeships, Erasmus Mundus, Vocational Education and Training and Youth exchanges before, during and after the experience. The Erasmus+ App currently offers the following **features**:

Access useful and structured information on the opportunities available under the Erasmus+ umbrella in one place in all EU languages, proving the great added value of the multilingual app:

- Keep track of the preparations for your mobility abroad, the tasks you have to do while you are away, as well as the ones needed upon your return, by using the Mobility Journey checklists;
- Find nice events and discounts near you from local student organisations;
- Read useful tips and stories written by other Erasmus+ participants and even submit your own;
- Find relevant services supporting your mobility experience;
- Status updates and notifications from relevant student services;
- Providing digital application procedure for Erasmus+ study mobility participants directly through the App;
- Support for generating a digital European Student Card via the App+.

Guiding Coordinators and Staff

- **The Erasmus Dashboard**
 - **How to Start Using the Dashboard**
 - **IIA's on Dashboard**
 - **Signing of IIAs**
 - **OLA on Dashboard**
 - **Short-Term Mobilities**

Guiding Coordinators and Staff

The Erasmus Dashboard

The Erasmus Dashboard (also known as the Erasmus Without Paper Dashboard) is a digital tool available to the HEIs in Europe. The Erasmus Dashboard is specially designed for institutions that do not currently use any digital solutions to manage their Erasmus+ mobility management. Developed with the support of the European Commission, the Dashboard can be utilized by the HEIs as a tool to manage their Erasmus+ mobility as per ESCI roadmap.

Dashboard offers the HEIs to review, decline, comment, download and sign incoming and outgoing students Learning Agreements online. In addition, the Dashboard connects to the European Commission's Erasmus+ Mobile App, allowing the coordinators or staff to communicate with the incoming and outgoing students directly via the App.

The Dashboard started hosting an EWP Inter-Institutional Agreement Manager in 2020. This allows for the establishment of IIAs through the Dashboard.

Erasmus Dashboard also allows for HEIs across Europe to indicate their Erasmus+ Covid-19 Mobility Status that is freely accessible to all students and partners alike at: <https://covid.uni-foundation.eu/>.

The Erasmus Dashboard is a powerful online tool available to all European HEIs free of charge.

How to Start Using the Dashboard

When working with the Erasmus Dashboard, it is important to keep in mind that each can only have one institutional account held by one person, and that is usually someone in the International Office or the Erasmus institutional Coordinator. If you would like to get an account, please contact your International Office as they have most probably already registered your institution in the Erasmus+ Dashboard. The institutional account holder can give access to as many users as needed in the institution and the following parts will shed light on this more in detail.

In the sidebar of Dashboard, on the left, you can see all the Dashboard sections and this guidebook will go through each one of them with more details.

Introduction and General Information

In the "My University" section, under general information, you can see the basic data of your university such as the name and the Erasmus code. Please note that the name that appears here was extracted from the official Erasmus Charter holder list, published by the European Commission, so it cannot be changed in any way before a new list is published.

Getting an Institutional Account

1. If your institution is not registered yet, create an account on <https://www.erasmus-dashboard.eu/institution/registration> (Step 1b).
 - a. **Log in** with your email and password.
 - b. **Register**: Only one main institutional account needs to be created per HEI (please remember to use an institutional email address), which can then nominate other staff members to use the Dashboard. Once your main institutional account has been validated by the EUF, you will receive an email.

The image shows two screenshots of the Erasmus Dashboard interface. The left screenshot is the main dashboard page, titled "Erasmus Dashboard", which describes the tool's purpose for HEIs and includes a "Login" and "Registration" button. The right screenshot shows the "Login" form with fields for "Email" and "Password", and a "Login" button. Below it is the "Institution registration" form, which includes fields for "Contact phone", "Contact email", "Institutional website", "Select country of institution", "(City) select a country first", and "(Institution) select a city first". It also has a checkbox for "I have read and agree to the Privacy Policy and Terms and Conditions" and a "Register" button.

2. If you encounter Duplicate Registrations follow the steps below:

Additional registrations cannot be submitted if the HEI already has the main institutional account (pending or confirmed). If a message below appears, please contact the main institutional account holder and/or International Relations Office to gain access to the platform and see more information about granting permission to the staff members of the institution in section below.

*Thank you for your interest in the Erasmus Dashboard. The Higher Education Institution you indicate in the registration data already has an Erasmus Dashboard account.
If you are trying to access the Dashboard as a staff member to sign/validate a Learning Agreement, please get in touch with your International Relations Office or the main institutional account holder, who can give you the necessary access to the system. Please also see more information [here](#)*

Opening Other Accounts

Staff Accounts

Once the validation of the main institutional account is confirmed, the HEI's main account can create as many individual accounts for their internal use as necessary, according to their specific management structures.

In the Erasmus Dashboard, under "Accounts and Access" the institutional account holder (the main international office or the Erasmus institutional coordinator) can design accounts and allocate access to the university staff depending on the task. In the Erasmus Dashboard, each university has only one institutional account. It is possible to make different types of accounts tailored for different kinds of accesses. For example, an account can be created only to view or sign and upload OLAs. It is also possible to create an account that can itself create and manage other accounts. The institutional account holder is not allowed to sign OLAs but it can create another separate account for managing OLAs, which might be necessary for smaller institutions where one single person handles everything. The institutional account holder does not show in the overview either.

HEI's main account can internally assign different roles (e.g. manage the student lists or fill in the information about the HEI that will be displayed in the Erasmus+ App etc.) to their staff members. These staff members can include coordinators, academic and administrative personnel. The assignment process will result in an e-mail notification to the staff which includes an invitation to the Erasmus Dashboard. After accepting this registration invitation, staff members will be directed to the Erasmus Dashboard and invited to create their login details to access the platform. Once the account is set up they can use it according to the permissions originally given to them.

The holder of the main institutional account can manage the list of staff members and their permissions at any time, as well as nominate more people involved in the organization of mobility. To match the specific working patterns in each institution, different levels of access to the Dashboard can be determined and associated with the roles — e.g. an 'Administrator' role allows to upload lists of nominated students and communicate with students, but not to create extra accounts or consent other colleagues' access to the Dashboard (see illustration below).

When accounts are created for new colleagues to access the Erasmus Dashboard, they will receive an automatic notification to generate their own password, which means they will have their own login credentials.

Multiuser access

Role name	Permissions		
Faculty Coordinator	Managing students	Remove	Edit
	Uploading students		
	Editing general info		
	Creating accounts		
	Editing step by step		
Administrator	Uploading students	Remove	Edit
	Editing step by step		
	Managing students		

Account management ?

Name	Email	Phone nr	Role	Action
	@uni.eu	+12	Administrator	Remove Edit
	@uni.eu	+12	Faculty Coordinator	Remove Edit

EWP Connection Settings

In order to exchange data through the EWP network, you need to tick the box to give consent of the exchange of data. This can only be done by some people in the institution. There are three boxes to be checked: the two ones refer to the use of IIA Manager, and the third one is for the OLA. These are all set to “No” by default. So if your HEI will use the Erasmus Dashboard for the EWP connection, you need to switch them to “Yes”. You may choose to only use the OLA or only use the IIA Manager in the Dashboard and then, of course, tick the boxes accordingly.

Organizational Units

“Organizational Units” is where as many new organizational units as wanted including all the departments or faculties of your institution can be made. IIAs can then be linked to these units. You can add new organizational units via this input form and clicking on “Add New”, and you can remove them by using “Remove” button. In some cases, you might prefer to keep the organizational units in your Dashboard account but you do not want to view it when using the IIA Manager. For just temporarily, you can simply deactivate the unit and re-activate it later on. Please note that deleting organizational units that are currently in a valid IIA is not possible.

My Account (Personal Settings)

The “My Settings” page is endowed with information of your specific user account, especially your role and the permissions enjoyed. If some permission you need is lacking, contact your main institutional account holder to see if your role can be changed. Finally, please note that

if you are the main institutional account holder, you will not see this tab since by default you have been given all available permissions.

Covid-19 Settings

The COVID-19 tool is one of the recent additions to the Erasmus+ Dashboard. In this section, you can indicate whether your institution is accepting exchange students and if you're also offering online classes, as well as a link to a specific page from your HEI's website that gives more details about it. This information will then be published on the COVID tool portal at the EUF website (<https://covid.uni-foundation.eu/>)

To update information about your institution, please follow these steps:

1. Go to <https://www.erasmus-dashboard.eu/account/login> and log in.
2. When you log in, you will be directed to the starting page of the Dashboard. On this page under the 'My University' section, you will see 'Covid-19'.
3. On the Covid-19 page, fill out the information for your institution in the specified fields and save. You can always update information as the situation changes.

The screenshot shows the 'My University > Covid 19' page. It features a left sidebar with navigation options like 'My University', 'Outgoing students', and 'Incoming students'. The main content area contains the following text and form fields:

To ensure that Higher Education Institutions and students across EU have more information on how the Covid-19 outbreak has impacted the upcoming academic semester, the collector below will publicly inform on the current situation in each HEI and can be updated as the situation evolves: <https://covid.uni-foundation.eu/>

Is your (host) university currently accepting exchange students for the start of the 2020/2021 academic year?
 Unknown No Yes

Can international students expect to follow classes online at your (host) university?
 Unknown No Yes

If available, please share a link to your University's information webpage on the impact of Covid-19 on international mobility:
Current URL defined:
New URL:

The information you enter, will automatically update the information on the EUF website.

In case you are **unable to access the Covid-19 section**, your colleagues can make sure that you have access in the following way:

1. Main institutional account holder or any staff member with permission to manage Accounts and Access set-up signs in.
2. Under 'Accounts and Access' a new role can be created, or an old one can be modified so that it includes the permission to access the Covid-19 settings (left-hand side of the page).
3. Add a new account and choose the newly created role (right-hand side of the page). The nominated staff will receive an email with which they can access the Dashboard and the Covid-19 settings.

Ukraine Settings

In response to the dramatic events unfolding in Ukraine Erasmus+ Dashboard have developed a portal to provide information about assistance offered by HEIs to students fleeing the war. If you would like to broadcast how your University is supporting these students, you can fill the answers below.

Does your Institution provide emergency shelter?

Unknown Yes No

Is health and psychological support made available at your Institution?

Unknown Yes No

Does your Institution provide a fast track application procedure for studies?

Unknown Yes No

Does your Institution offer special scholarships for studies?

Unknown Yes No

Please provide a link to your Institution's dedicated webpage with more information on this topic, or to your Institution's relevant contacts page.

URL:

Other Settings

Another very recent addition in the Erasmus+ Dashboard is **Applications for Erasmus+** tool. This tool allows the HEIs to receive Erasmus+ applications through the Dashboard, to set the application period for each semester and other requirements for application. After saving these settings on the Dashboard, they are published on Erasmus+ App.

Application Settings

Autumn/Winter semester/annual Application Period *	Start Date	End Date
	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Spring/Summer semester/annual Application Period *	Start Date	End Date
	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Max number of priorities of host HEI per student application *	<input type="text" value="3"/>	

[Save & Publish Application Settings on the Erasmus+ App](#)

Requirements for Outgoing Students

Please check the boxes of the files that are required for the Outgoing Students of your HEI and provide the relevant URLs and descriptions.

Documents Required	CV <input type="checkbox"/>	CV is not required
	Motivation Letter <input type="checkbox"/>	Motivation Letter is not required
	Transcript of Records <input type="checkbox"/>	Transcript of Records is not required
	External Certification <input type="checkbox"/>	External Certification is not required
	Recommendation Letter <input type="checkbox"/>	Recommendation Letter is not required
	Other Document <input type="checkbox"/>	Other Document is not required
	Language Level <input type="checkbox"/>	Language Level is not required

Please check the boxes of the fields that are required for the Outgoing Students of your HEI and provide the relevant URLs and descriptions.

Other fields	Reference Contact <input type="checkbox"/>	Reference Contact is not required
	Portfolio <input type="checkbox"/>	Portfolio is not required
	Other Requirement <input type="checkbox"/>	Other Requirement is not required

IAs on Dashboard

An inter-institutional agreement (IIA) is an agreement setting the framework conditions for the student and staff mobilities between institutions funded by the Erasmus+ programme. It can be signed between two or more HEIs. Thanks to the Dashboard, HEIs can create their digital IIAs to save time and paper.

The **IIA Manager** tab on the left column in the Dashboard is where you can find everything you need to create, organize, sign and import your IIAs.

How to Create an IIA

A new IIA can be created in the **New Digital IIA** section under IIA manager, which is on the left column of the Dashboard interface. To create an IIA, you must first accept the [Terms & Conditions and Privacy Policy](#) by checking in the confirmation box to be able to press the “**Next Page**” button. On the next page, you can start to organize the details for the intended new agreement.

The screenshot shows the 'IIA Manager > New Digital IIA' interface. The left sidebar contains navigation options: Dashboard β, Outgoing students, Incoming students, Requirements, IIA manager (IIA List, New Digital IIA, Import IIA, Default IIA Data, FAQs), EWP (Website, Settings), Support (FAQs, Tutorials, Documentation), and External Services. The main content area is titled 'Key Action 1 - Mobility of learners and staff - Higher Education Student and Staff Mobility between Programme Countries Requirements for Inter-Institutional Agreements 2021-20[29]'. It includes a section for 'Static information applicable to all Inter-Institutional Agreements' with a paragraph of text and a 'Grading systems of the institutions' section with a recommendation and a confirmation checkbox. A green message states: 'The IIAs of your institution are managed by the Dashboard in the EWP network so you will be able to send this agreement through the EWP Network.' At the bottom, there are buttons for 'Clear IIA', 'Previous Page', 'Next Page', 'Submit IIA', 'Add Cooperation Condition', and 'Delete Cooperation Condition'.

Partner Details

The **Partner Details** section on this page will show the name and data of your institution automatically. Under the details, you will need to choose an organizational unit, i.e. the Department for which you want to organize the mobility. The Data will be pulled from the account that you are going to use when you select the organizational unit that will be forming the IIA. The sections under the titles **General**, **Faculty/Faculties** and **Course Catalog** can only be filled manually for now.

After filling in the details of your institution, then it is time to complete the details of your partner institution. Under the **Partner Details** section, you will see a dropdown menu of “Institutions Available for IIA”. You should find your partner institution by their **Erasmus Code** in the list. You can obtain this Code either by contacting the partner institution, or by searching in the ECHE database.²¹

²¹ The weblink for the search is <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/erasmus-esc/index/organisations/search-for-an-organisation>.

Creator Details

Institution Name Izmir Institute of Technology	Erasmus Code TR IZMIR03	Country Turkey
City Izmir		
Organizational Unit Food Engineering		
Contact Name Doc. Dr. Efe	Contact Email erasmuskoordinator@iyte.edu.tr	Contact Phone +902327
Websites		
General www.iyte.edu.tr	Faculty/Faculties https://food.iyte.edu.tr/	Course Catalogue https://obs.iyte.edu.tr/oibs/b

Partner Details ?

Institutions available (Select an institution)	Erasmus Code (Required)	Institution Name (Required)
	Country	City
Organizational Unit Select OU		
Contact Name	Contact Email	Contact Phone
Websites		
General	Faculty/Faculties	Course Catalogue

After selecting the institution, its name, city and country information will be filled in automatically. The system will then notify you with a green info text about if the IIAs of the partner institution is managed by EWP network or the Dashboard.

For example;

The IIAs of the partner are managed by a node in the EWP network. This agreement will be sent through the EWP Network.

or

The IIAs of the partner are managed by the Dashboard in the EWP network. This agreement will not be sent through the EWP Network and treated internally in the Dashboard.

The partner using a different management tool for managing the IIA will not change workflow of creating an IIA. But if the partner is not connected to the EWP network at all, you will not be able to find their name on the dropdown menu.

After choosing the name of the partner institution, info for contact details may or may not appear depending on the data they provided. This information is not required to fill in but selecting the Academic Year (start and end) of the IIA is necessary. All of the notifications regarding this new IIA will be sent to your partner through this email address. The other sections can be left for your partner to fill in.

By clicking Next Page, you will proceed to Your Static Information page which is about the nomination dates of your institution for the incoming students. If you want to edit this page, you can do so in the Default IIA Data section from the menu on the left.

If your static information does not require any change, you just click Next Page where you will proceed to Page 1 of the Cooperation Conditions.

Cooperation Conditions

In the next steps, the partners can indicate the cooperation conditions for all types of mobilities. If you want to add more than one type of mobility, you have to add a new cooperation condition. You can create multiple cooperation conditions for a single agreement with a specific direction and mobility type.

IIA Manager > New Digital IIA

Terms of the agreement to be set for each agreement and approved by the institutions (Information only accessible to the relevant parties).
Cooperation conditions (page 1)

Mobility numbers per academic year

The partners commit to amend the table below in case of changes in the mobility data by no later than the end of September in the preceding academic year.

Sender Erasmus Code TR IZMIR03	Receiver Erasmus Code
Sending Organizational Unit Civil Engineering	Receiving Organizational Unit International Relations Office
Mobilities Per Year 5	
Subject area	
ISCED-F Code 0732 - Building and civil engineer	ISCED - Clarification Building and civil engineering
<input type="button" value="Delete"/>	
<input type="button" value="Add"/>	
Mobility Type Student studies	Total Months Per Year Per Mobility 6

In this section, you need to insert your **ISCED-F Code** which is basically the field of education and training that is closest to the subject of the degree to be awarded to the trainee by the sending institution.²² To inform incoming students about the expected language skills you can fill in the tabs under **Recommended Language Skills** title specifying the Language of Instruction and the Recommended Language(s) Instruction Level.

You can also add other comments or recommendations to the end of the page under the title Any Other Information Regarding the Terms of the Agreement.

At this point, you may choose to move forward to the next page, deleting your cooperation conditions or create a new additional cooperation condition. Deleting a cooperation condition can be done easily at the right bottom of the screen. Moving forward to the next page will bring you the whole review of your newly created IIA.

Mobility Types

Selecting an Organizational Unit is not mandatory but you will have to enter a number for the **Mobilities Per Year**, which is going to show the number of students that you prefer to attend the mobility for the specific unit, subject, and mobility type (student studies, student traineeship, staff teacher, staff training). Entering a study cycle restriction to the specific mobility is also possible in this section.

Submitting an IIA Proposal

If everything is fine, you can sign and submit the IIA. But pressing the “Sign and Submit IIA” button is not going to put the final signature on the agreement. By pressing the *sign* button for the first time simply puts forward a proposal for the partner to review and sign. At this point, the partner will either sign the agreement or edit it.

Editing Changes to the IIAs

If the partner signs the agreement at the first attempt, the status of the IIA will change to *signed*. If they choose to edit it before signing, they will hit *the update* and *sign* button afterward and their proposed changes will be sent back to you.

²² The [ISCED-F search tool](http://ec.europa.eu/education/tools/isced-f_en.htm) is available at http://ec.europa.eu/education/tools/isced-f_en.htm

Signing of IIAs

Only after the responsible person in your HEI has finalized the agreement, your partner will have to put the definitive signature. You can either edit the agreement again or put the final signature. After putting the final signature, you will not be able to edit it again.

Importing IIAs

Upload CSV file to import Inter-Institutional Agreements

The Inter-Institutional Agreement import functionality now supports the CSV upload. Upon entering the data you can overview the agreements one-by-one to make sure all the information is correct and submit the data. This action will trigger a creation of pre-filled Inter-Institutional Agreement and a notification for the partner inviting it to edit or sign the document. It is also possible to submit all agreements at the same time by clicking on the 'Import all' button. The format of the CSV file can be verified through the use of a template spreadsheet made available on the EWP CC [here](#).

I confirm, also on behalf of my HEI, that I have all the authorisations, including the consent of the relevant natural persons, necessary to upload the personal data and information I am providing, pursuant to the Dashboard [Terms & Conditions and Privacy Policy](#).

Dosya seçilmedi

The **Import IIA** option on the left menu allows you to upload your IIAs to the system with a specifically built-in CSV file that will have been prefilled by you. You can acquire this file by clicking on [here](#) in the explanations of the same page. It is an alternate option to the **New Digital IIA** option and allows the users to import a bulk of IIAs at once instead of adding them one by one.

Before uploading your CSV file, you need to decide if the file will be listing the students' study mobility IIAs only or the IIAs with four mobility types. For the first one, you can download a template created by the EUF [here](#). For the second one, another template prepared by the EUF is ready for use [here](#).

To upload the file, it is obligatory to agree with the *Terms & Conditions and Privacy Policy* by checking in the box in front of the description.

Once you have chosen the correct file, click on **View and import** to display all the data. The system will automatically read the data in the CSV file, given that the column **headers have not been modified** or removed.

Once the correct file is browsed from your PC and uploaded, you are going to see the options **View and Import** and **Import All**. By clicking on **View and Import** you will be able to review the IIA to check all the data you input, if the column headers have not been modified or removed the system will automatically read the data in the CSV file.

You should make sure that everything is correct and no information is missing. If you have uploaded more than one IIA at a time (i.e. multiple rows of CSV file), you can move back and forth between them to view the data of each IIA by clicking **Next** and **Previous IIA** buttons.

Once you have confirmed each IIA, you can do one of two things: by clicking on **Submit this IIA, the current IIA displayed** will be uploaded. In other words, if the CSV file has multiple IIAs, **only the displayed will be uploaded**, unless you click **Submit this IIA** on each one of them.

Alternatively, you can where you can upload all IIAs at the same time by clicking on **Import All**. A pop-up asking for confirmation will appear and if you press **Ok**, the upload will start, clearly showing which IIA is getting uploaded. Please be careful with this last step because if something was wrong with your CSV file, you can still view the IIA and you may not notice anything wrong or missing, but the upload would be interrupted and one or more error messages would pop up.

Other Features

Listing IIAs

Under the **IIA Manager** menu, you will see the **IIA List** as the first subtitle. The **IIA List** allows you to filter and search specific IIAs.

Choose a field to sort and its direction

Under this title, you can filter your IIAs by IIA ID, Status, Partner Erasmus Code, Partner Contact, Creator Sign Date, Creator Sign Contact, Partner Sign Date and Partner Sign Contact options. Based on the criteria selected, the agreements can also be sorted in ascending or descending order. After entering the filters, you need to press the **Apply Changes** button to see the results. Navigation through the listed IIAs can be done by clicking on the page numbers on top of the bar, or by clicking **next** or **last** page. Under the IIA listed (depending on their status) on the right side of the sorting options, you will see the options to **Edit**, **View and Sign**, and **Delete** options. If you can only see the view button, that means the IIA is being reviewed by your partner or has already been signed by both parties.

Search for IIAs in EWP

This search function can be used for finding the IIAs with the partners on the EWP network. After pressing the search button, you will have the option to sort out the agreements by Partner Erasmus Code, Academic Year, and Modified Since options.

OLA on Dashboard

General information on OLA

The OLA is a digital tool that can be used for managing the Learning Agreement, one of the most important steps of any Erasmus Exchange. For insuring the recognition of the ECTS credits earned abroad, OLA can be defined as the most convenient way of getting approval from the home and the host institutions for the courses taken abroad during Erasmus Exchange. The OLA enables mobile higher education students to prepare, sign and submit their learning agreements online. Similarly, HEIs will use OLA to replace paper learning agreements. Using OLA, HEIs can manage the learning agreement and signing procedures remotely, it also enables them moving from a paper version to a fully digital one.

To use OLA through Dashboard, you need to tick the box(es) on the EWP settings section of the Dashboard to agree on the exchange of data. When the OLA box in the EWP settings section of the Dashboard is checked, the Erasmus Dashboard will represent your HEI in the EWP network for electronic exchange of OLA information.

E+ Dashboard β Ewp > Settings

Current SCHAC code for the EWP Network: iyte.edu.tr

Do you agree that the Dashboard represents your higher education institution in the EWP Network to exchange inter-institutional agreements with your partners?

No Yes

Do you agree that the Dashboard represents your higher education institution in the EWP Network to exchange the static information for inter-institutional agreements with your partners?

No Yes

Should the Dashboard represent your higher education institution in the EWP Network for the purpose of enabling the electronic exchange of the Online Learning Agreement information?

No Yes

E+ Dashboard β Outgoing Student > OLA

< Go back

Learning Agreement info

LA-id LA-231136

Status Signed By Student

Academic Year 2022/2023

Planned Period From 2022-02-07

Planned Period To 2022-07-01

Created 2022-06-19

Student Personal data

Firstname		Gender	Male
Lastname		Nationality	Turkey
Email	elbir@std.iyte.edu.tr	Field of education (ISCED)	Information and Communication Technologies (06)

How to list and filter students

At the section Mobilities OLA 3.0, a full list of both inbound and outbound OLA's can be listed. Clicking on the "outgoing students" or "incoming students" you will see the full list displayed under those titles. The list can be narrowed down to what you are specifically searching for by using the filters. The filtration can be done by name of the student, by the status of the OLA, by country, by the Erasmus code of the host institution, or by academic year. The default of the system is set to the current academic year. Keeping the generic "All Academic Years" filter might help you if a student chooses the wrong academic year while filling in the OLA.

E+ Dashboard β **Mobilities (OLA 3.0) > Outgoing Students**

My University
 General info
 Accounts and Access
 Organizational Units
 My settings
 Covid-19
 Ukraine
 Logout

Mobilities (OLA 3.0)
 Outgoing students
 Incoming students
 Upload

Short-Term Mobilities
 Outgoing students

Select a filter for the table
 Search
 Select status
 Select status
 Unsigned
 Changes unsigned
 Changes signed by student
 Changes signed by student/sending
 Changes signed by student/sending/receiving
 Signed by student/sending
 Signed by student
 Signed by student/sending/receiving
 Reset

Number of Learning Agreements: 1

Instructions
 Search bar to filter student name, start/end mobility, the coordinators, emails of all involved, faculty names and HEI name.

First Name	Last Name	Start Mobility	End Mobility	Status
		2022-02-07	2022-07-01	Signed By Student

E+ Dashboard β **Mobilities (OLA 3.0) > Outgoing Students**

Units
 My settings
 Covid-19
 Ukraine
 Logout

Mobilities (OLA 3.0)
 Outgoing students
 Incoming students
 Upload

Short-Term Mobilities
 Outgoing students
 Incoming students

Mobilities (OLA 2.0)
 Outgoing students

Select a filter for the table
 Search
 Select status
 2021/2022
 Select academic year
 2019/2020
 2020/2021
 2021/2022
 2022/2023
 2023/2024
 All academic years
 Reset

Number of Learning Agreements: 76

Instructions
 Search bar to filter student name, start/end mobility, the coordinators, emails of all involved, faculty names and HEI name.

First Name	Last Name	Start Mobility	End Mobility	Status
	K...	2022-02-01	2022-06-01	Signed By Student/!
	C...	2022-02-01	2022-06-01	Signed By Student/!
	K...	2022-02-01	2022-06-01	Signed By Student/!
	C...	2022-02-28	2022-06-12	Signed By Student/!
	A...	2022-02-28	2022-07-15	Signed By Student/Sending/Rx
	U...	2022-03-01	2022-07-30	Signed By Student/!

E+ Dashboard β **Mobilities (OLA 3.0) > Outgoing Students**

Units
 My settings
 Covid-19
 Ukraine
 Logout

Mobilities (OLA 3.0)
 Outgoing students
 Incoming students
 Upload

Short-Term Mobilities
 Outgoing students
 Incoming students

Mobilities (OLA 2.0)
 Outgoing students

Select a filter for the table
 Search
 Select status
 2021/2022
 EE TALLINN04
 Select HEI Erasmus Code
 A GRAZ09
 A LINZ01
 CZ PRAHA01
 D BERLIN04
 D ESSLING03
 D HEIDELB01
 D MUEHEIM01
 D RAVENSBO01
 EE TALLINN04
 G EGALCO02
 G VOLOS01
 HR SPLIT01
 HU BUDAPES01
 I HILANO01
 I NAPOLI01

First Name	Last Name	Start Mobility	End Mobility	Status
		2022-01-24	2022-06-12	Signed By Student/Sending/Rx

First Name	Last Name	Start Mobility	End Mobility	Status
P...	S...	2022-02-22	2022-07-08	Signed By Student/...
S...	S...	2022-02-22	2022-07-08	Signed By Student/...
P...	P...	2022-02-22	2022-07-08	Signed By Student/...
V...	T...	2022-02-28	2022-07-13	Signed By Student/...

How to sign and decline OLA

You can view a general overview of the learning agreement when you open it. After checking the information and details on the document you can sign or decline it. Every time you revise the OLA a new revised version will appear in the system. Declining to sign an OLA will not delete the document from the system. All the signatures will be removed from the document once you or the other institution declines it, and it will be returned back to the student to edit it. You can use the “comments” field to let the student know the reason of the rejection. It is important to use this section so the student will know what to do when the document is returned to them for editing. Also, if you have anything that you want the student to change, you should let the student know in the comments section. All the comments on the document will be emailed to the student. The student will only be able edit an OLA that he/she signed only if it is declined.

Outgoing Student > OLA

Commitment
By digitally signing this document, the student, the Sending Institution and the Receiving Institution confirm that they approve the Learning Agreement and that they will comply with all the arrangements agreed by all parties. Sending and Receiving Institutions undertake to apply all the principles of the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education relating to mobility for studies (or the principles agreed in the Inter-Institutional Agreement for institutions located in Partner Countries). The Beneficiary Institution and the student should also commit to what is set out in the Erasmus+ grant agreement. The Receiving Institution confirms that the educational components listed are in line with its course catalogue and

Fill in reason of declining*

We want to draw your attention that by declining OLA, all the signatures will be removed and student(s) will be able to edit the Online Learning Agreement to introduce your proposed changes. Your comments will be emailed to the student(s).

Other OLA fields and Automatic Recognition

The sections of the OLA (Student Information, Sending Institution Information, Institution Information Receiver, Recommended Mobility Programme, Persons Responsible and Commitment) are entirely the template given by the European Commission. Therefore, these fields of the OLA cannot be changed.

E+ Dashboard β **Outgoing Student > OLA**

My University

- General info
- Accounts and Access
- Organizational Units
- My settings
- Covid-19
- Ukraine
- Logout

Mobilities (OLA 3.0)

- Outgoing students
- Incoming students
- Upload

Short-Term Mobilities

- Outgoing students

Sending institution info

Name	Izmir Institute of Technology	Contact person	...
Country	Turkey	Contact email	...@iyte.edu.tr
Erasmus Code	TR IZMIR03	Contact phone	...07898
Address	Izmir	Res. person	...demir
Faculty	Mechanical Engineering	Res. email	...@iyte.edu.tr
		Res. phone	...06787

Receiving institution info

Name	Univerza v Mariboru	Contact person	...Olga Sevic
Country	Slovenia	Contact email	...@erasmus@um.si
Erasmus Code	SI MARIBOR01	Contact phone	...5238
Address	Maribor	Res. person	...Olga Sevic
Faculty	Mechanical Engineering	Res. email	...@um.si

E+ Dashboard β **Outgoing Student > OLA**

14U110 Sports I 3 Second semester (Summer/Spring)

Total ECTS credits 30

Learning Agreement Table B

Code	Subject title	ECTS	Semester	Automatic Recognition
54U005	Textile Testing	6	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	Yes
14U064	Renewable Energy Sources	6	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	Yes
ME328	Manufacturing Engineering	6	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	Yes
54U038	Polymer Materials Recycling	6	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	Yes
54U017	Ecology and Environmental Protection	3	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	Yes
14U110	Sports I	3	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	Yes
Total ECTS credits		30		

E+ Dashboard β **Outgoing Student > OLA**

Res. phone +386...

Learning Agreement Table A

Code	Subject title	ECTS	Semester
54U005	Textile Testing	6	Second semester (Summer/Spring)
14U064	Renewable Energy Sources	6	Second semester (Summer/Spring)
14V077	Production Management	6	Second semester (Summer/Spring)
54U038	Polymer Materials Recycling	6	Second semester (Summer/Spring)
54U017	Ecology and Environmental Protection	3	Second semester (Summer/Spring)
14U110	Sports I	3	Second semester (Summer/Spring)
Total ECTS credits		30	

Learning Agreement Table B

Code	Subject title	ECTS	Semester	Automatic Recognition
------	---------------	------	----------	-----------------------

Erasmus Dashboard has the latest updates from the Commission. "Auto Recognition" is the new part of OLA and this field is set to "Yes" according to the rules of the programme. By keeping this default selection (YES), the home institution confirms that all credits earned at the host institution – as agreed in the OLA and verified by the Transcript of Records – will be transferred on time and counted towards the students' degree without any extra work or assessment of the student.

Code	Subject title	ECTS	Semester	Automatic Recognition
O1	Other courses	6	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Total ECTS credits		30		
Learning Agreement Table B				
IT1	Introduction to IT	8	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
P1	Programming 1	8	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
M1	Mathematics 1	8	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
O1	Optional class	6	Second semester (Summer/Spring)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Total ECTS credits		30		

The official guidelines of the European Commission states that, if you, as a coordinator, wish to uncheck the "Automatic Recognition" box, you must provide a specific reason and an indication of what kind of official recognition will be used.

As per official guidelines from the European Commission, if the automatic recognition will not take place, please provide a clear justification and an indication on what other type of formal recognition will be applied.

Fill in reason of rejecting

I

How to upload an OLA

It is possible to upload a CSV file to pre-fill multiple OLAs at the same time. Up to 25 OLA's can be uploaded to the system at the same time using a CSV file. But it should be remembered that this feature is only available for outgoing students, not for incoming students. The CSV

file template for this process is available on the Erasmus Without Paper Competence Center and it is mandatory to fill in all fields of the CSV file.

By following the above steps, you will be able to create a pre-filled OLA and the students are going to receive automatic invitations as email notifications to finalize their document.

Short-Term Mobilities

Since 2021, short-term mobility (Short-term mobility and mobility blended with short-term physical mobility) is a new part of the OLA platform. The only difference here is that you cannot upload the list of students by filling in a CSV file. To manage the short term mobilities you can use the related menu in the Erasmus Dashboard.

The same options are available as semester mobility management to sort/search/filter student lists and, also to send further comments to the students or to sign the OLA.

Mobilities OLA 2.0

Older OLAs, formed during the 2014-2020 program periods ending in June 2021, from both outgoing and incoming students are archived in the Mobility OLA 2.0 section of the Dashboard. If you have used the Dashboard in the past, you can find the OLA of your former outgoing and incoming students in this section. The new OLA created today will not be visible in Mobilities OLA 2.0 but in Mobilities OLA3.0.

Mobilities OLA 3.0

The Mobility OLA 3.0 section is connected to the new updated OLA platform where the students can prepare, sign and submit OLAs. The OLA platform has been completely renewed at October 2020. The new OLA tool has a powerful software architecture which makes it more secure. It now has a more advanced engine that brings new opportunities with respect to interconnecting it to the EWP ecosystem and other digital tools. The new tool has an interface that allows simplified navigation and makes it more accessible to students.

First Name	Last Name	Start Mobility	End Mobility	Status
		2022-02-28	2022-07-22	Signed By Student/Sending/R
		2022-03-01	2022-06-03	Signed By Student/Sending/R
		2022-02-28	2022-07-01	Signed By Student
		2022-02-01	2022-08-01	Signed By Student
		2022-02-28	2022-07-01	Signed By Student

Supporting Universities in the
Digital Transformation in Erasmus+

Note on Authors' Contribution

The authors from each project partner contributed to different sections in the guidebook. The information regarding these sections and their contributors can be found below, according to the order of sections in the Guidebook:

Joachim Wyssling from the European University Foundation (EUF) wrote the Introduction. For the part of Getting Connected, each project partner HEIs explained the situation in their institutions. According to the order in the Guidebook; Abdulkadir Gölcü and Ömer Kavrar from Selçuk University (SU) for SU; José Juan Pazos Arias, Roi Martínez Portela, Sergio Arcay Mallo and Martín López Nores from Vigo University (VU) for VU; Luca Ferri, Ilaria Martino and Flavio Spagnuolo from the University of Naples Federico II (UNINA) for UNINA; and Asena Altan, Bengü Aydın Dikmen, Gizem Köfünçeli and Nur Başak Sürmeli Eraltuğ from Izmir Institute of Technology (IZTECH) for IZTECH elaborated on the institutional experience of digital transformation of their Erasmus mobility processes. Joachim Wyssling also wrote the section on the identification and access management of users. The section on the Online Learning Agreement (OLA) was prepared by José Juan Pazos Arias, Roi Martínez Portela, Sergio Arcay Mallo, and Martín López Nores from VU. The following section which is on the Erasmus+ App was prepared by Luca Ferri, Ilaria Martino, and Flavio Spagnuolo from UNINA. The part on Erasmus+ Dashboard was written by Asena Altan, Bengü Aydın Dikmen, Gizem Köfünçeli and Nur Başak Sürmeli Eraltuğ from IZTECH.

ISBN 978-625-00-1002-0

December, 2022

Prepared by Izmir Institute of Technology as part of
Intellectual Output 5 of SUDTE Project

SELÇUK
UNIVERSITY
KONYA - 1975

İZMİR
INSTITUTE OF
TECHNOLOGY

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI
DI NAPOLI FEDERICO II

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SUDTE

Supporting Universities in the
Digital Transformation Erasmus+
